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Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Post-Primary Education Children in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among internally displaced post-primary education children in Benue State, Nigeria. The study population comprises 68,076 school-age children during the 2024/2025 academic session from six Local Government Areas in Benue State, Nigeria, with a sample of 384 participants selected through multistage sampling. Data were collected using a validated structured questionnaire, Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (TETAQEIDCQ), which achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used for analysis. Findings reveal that technology-enhanced tools significantly improve access to quality education and positively influence learning outcomes among internally displaced post-primary education children in Benue State, Nigeria. The study highlights the importance of integrating technology to bridge educational gaps for displaced learners. Recommendations include enhancing digital infrastructure, providing teacher training, and implementing policies that support equitable access to educational technology for IDP children.

Keywords: Assessment, Education, Impact, Internally Displaced Persons & Technology

Introduction

At the end of 2019, it is estimated that 45.7 million people were internally displaced by conflict and violence. Close to 20 million of the people internally displaced by conflict and violence are children (IDMC, 2020). A United Nations Educational and Scientific Organization (UNESCO, 2023) report also indicates that Nigeria is still home to about 20 million out-of-school children, with persons with disabilities occupying a sizeable

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percentage. United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2015) reported that 800,000 children in Nigeria are affected by the Boko Haram insurgency, with 19 out of 42 camps lacking educational access as of June 2015 (Global Educational Monitoring Report [GEMR], 2016). The UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon, in the 2015 General Assembly, revealed that over 60 million people globally are displaced, impacting children who lose educational opportunities, some coerced into becoming child soldiers (National Emergency Management Agency [NEMA], 2015). The National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) reported in 2015 that 2.5 million people, with 1.2 million school-age children, were displaced in northern Nigeria due to Boko Haram attacks, with 56% being children under 18 and over half under 5 years old (NEMA, 2015).

The global phenomenon of internal displacement has led to a significant number of children facing disruptions in their education, stemming from forced relocations and the resultant instability. Among these affected populations, Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) children are particularly vulnerable, often experiencing limited access to educational resources and facing challenges in maintaining a consistent learning environment. The vast majority of children internally displaced are denied a secure, inclusive, and quality education, along with the numerous short- and long-term benefits it provides. Obviously, barriers such as a lack of good teaching capacity, limited funding, ongoing insecurity, social tensions and discrimination compound with education systems in low-income and fragile contexts which are already overstretched (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2020).

Consequently, the integration of technology into education has emerged as a potential catalyst for addressing these issues. With the growing interest in the adoption of technology in Nigeria's education sector, the use of technology for teaching and learning has proven to be an enabler of equitable education for persons with disabilities, learners from disadvantaged backgrounds, learners living in rural locations, and women and girls of marginalized groups (Thisdaylive, 2023).

In recent years, various technological interventions, such as online learning platforms, mobile applications, and digital educational resources, have been implemented to enhance educational access for marginalized populations, including IDP children. UNHCR (2016) in their study on the technology as an enabler for equity and inclusion in education sees technology as a veritable tool to drive inclusion in education among refugees. These tools offer the prospect of delivering quality educational content

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regardless of geographical constraints, potentially bridging the gap created by displacement.

However, the impact of technology on educational outcomes for IDP children is a complex interplay of opportunities and challenges. On the positive side, technology can provide flexible learning environments, personalized instruction, and opportunities for remote collaboration. Yet, challenges such as limited infrastructure, digital literacy gaps, and the potential exacerbation of existing inequalities need to be critically examined.

Ultimately, this study provides a crucial examination of how technology impacts the accessibility and quality of post-primary education for internally displaced children (IDP) in Benue State. By comparing our findings with existing literature, several key insights and gaps become evident. Uzodinma, Njoku, and Ejiofor (2024) explore the broader role of technology in enhancing educational outcomes across various levels in Nigeria, highlighting its potential to improve learning experiences. Their findings underscore the importance of integrating technology into educational settings but do not specifically focus on the unique challenges faced by IDP children in post-primary education.

Similarly, Omale, Abduljabbar, and Dauda (2022) address the urgent need to bridge educational gaps for IDP children through targeted interventions during emergencies. Their work emphasizes the necessity of tailored strategies to support displaced students but does not delve deeply into the specific technological solutions that could address these gaps. Ambe-Uva (2012) also discusses the potential of open and distance learning as a means to uphold the right to education for displaced populations in Nigeria. This perspective is valuable but primarily focuses on higher-level educational solutions rather than the practical, on-the-ground impact of technology in post-primary education settings for IDP children.

The gap identified by this study is the need for a focused examination of how technology specifically impacts the educational experiences and outcomes of IDP children in post-primary education in Benue State. While existing studies provide a general understanding of technology's role and the challenges faced by displaced populations, they do not offer a detailed assessment of how technological interventions can be tailored to the unique needs of IDP children in this specific educational context. This

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research aims to bridge this gap by providing a nuanced analysis of technological impacts and offering actionable insights to develop more effective strategies for leveraging technology to enhance access to quality education for IDP children in Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

This study addresses the pressing issue of internal displacement, with a specific focus on the vulnerable demographic of IDP children in Nigeria, particularly in Benue State. The unique challenges faced by IDP children include limited access to educational resources and difficulties in maintaining a consistent learning environment due to forced relocations and the resultant instability. The majority of these displaced children are denied a secure, inclusive, and quality education, exacerbating the short- and long-term consequences of their displacement (IDMC, 2020). Existing barriers, such as a lack of teaching capacity, limited funding, ongoing insecurity, social tensions, and discrimination, further compound the challenges faced by education systems in low-income and fragile contexts (IDMC, 2020). Recognizing the potential of technology to address these issues, the study acknowledges the growing interest in adopting technology in Nigeria's education sector. Technological interventions, such as online learning platforms, mobile applications, and digital educational resources, have shown promise in enhancing educational access for marginalized populations, including IDP children. The study aligns with the perspective presented by (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees [UNHCR], 2023), which views technology as a valuable tool for driving inclusion in education among refugees, transcending geographical constraints and bridging gaps created by displacement. Despite numerous studies on IDPs, none have explored the impact of technology on the educational outcomes of IDP children. Additionally, there is a lack of standardized structures, well-articulated plans, and procedures in Nigeria to address digital educational needs in emergencies. Given the contemporary and ongoing nature of this issue, a research gap has emerged, prompting this study to fill the void.

Purpose of the Study

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The aim of this research is to scrutinize the technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among internally displaced post-primary education children in Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives guiding the study are to:

- a) Assess the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State.
- b) Examine the impact of technology-enhanced-tools compared to traditional method on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be set out to guide the study:

- 1) What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?
- 2) What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools compared to traditional method on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?

Methodology

The research design for this study adopted a descriptive survey design to systematically collect and analyze data on the experiences of internally displaced children (IDCs) in post-primary schools across Benue State.

This design was appropriate for assessing the impact of technology on access to quality education without manipulating variables (Nworgu, 2015). The study was conducted in Benue State, focusing on three major IDP camps: Abagena (Makurdi), Gbajimba (Guma), and Anyiin (Logo).

These areas were selected due to their high concentration of displaced persons and evident challenges in accessing quality education. The population consisted of 68,076 school-age IDCs (35,460 males and 32,616 females) across six Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Benue State, based on data from the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) Round 11 (March 2023) and the Biometric Registration Progress Report (July 2024). A sample of 384 school-age IDCs was selected using a multistage sampling technique.

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First, proportional stratified sampling determined the sample from each camp: Makurdi (124), Guma (146), and Logo (113). Within each camp, stratification by gender was applied based on a 52:48 male-to-female ratio. Finally, simple random sampling was employed within each gender stratum to ensure equal selection chances.

A structured questionnaire titled *Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (TETAQEIDCQ)*, adapted from Balogun (2005), was used. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A (demographics) and Section B (25 items grouped into five thematic clusters). Responses were rated using a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1).

Experts in measurement and evaluation validated the instrument for clarity and relevance. Following validation, a pilot test with 20 participants was conducted outside the study area. Cronbach's Alpha yielded reliability coefficients ranging from 0.70 to 0.79 across clusters, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data were collected using a direct delivery-and-retrieval method by the researcher and three trained assistants. Clear instructions were provided, and responses were retrieved immediately to minimize non-response and ensure data integrity. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to analyze the research questions, with a mean score of 2.50 or higher indicating a high extent of agreement.

Presentation of Results

This provides concise summary of the data analysis conducted following the administration of the research instrument. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were employed to analyze respondents' responses. These measures facilitated informed decision-making regarding the outcomes of the study.

Descriptive Analysis

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Table 1: The demographic description of respondents:

Age	Frequency	Percent
11-13	54	14.1
14-16	186	48.4
17-19	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	196	51.0
Female	188	49.0
Total	384	100.0
Class Level		
JSS1-3	250	65.1
SS1-3	134	34.9
Total	384	100.0
Duration in the IDP camp		
Less than one year	27	7.0
1-2 years	330	85.9
More than 2 years	27	7.0
Total	384	100.0

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Table 1 provides a demographic overview of a sample population (N = 384) with variables categorized by age, gender, class level, and duration of stay in an IDP camp in Benue State.

Age Distribution

The age range of 14-16 years comprises the majority (48.4%) of the population, followed by 17-19 years (37.5%), while 11-13 years accounts for the smallest proportion (14.1%). This suggests that the population is predominantly adolescents in middle-to-late teenage years, likely indicative of the targeted group for the study.

Gender Distribution

The gender ratio is nearly balanced, with males constituting 51.0% and females 49.0%. The near parity ensures gender representation in the study, allowing for potentially unbiased gender-specific analysis.

Class Level Distribution

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A significant portion of the participants (65.1%) are in Junior Secondary School (JSS 1-3), while 34.9% are in Senior Secondary School (SS 1-3). This distribution highlights the dominance of younger secondary school students, which might influence the type of interventions or programs implemented.

Years spent in the IDP Camp

Most participants (85.9%) have stayed in the camp for 1-2 years, with only 7.0% each having stayed less than a year or more than two years. This indicates a relatively recent displacement, as the majority have spent a moderate duration in the camp. It reflects the likely ongoing impact of displacement on education and other life domains.

Research Question 1: What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Technology's Role in Increasing Access to Education for IDP Children in Benue State

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Technology has improved my access to educational materials.		2.77	0.57	Agreed
2.	The use of online learning platforms has made it easier for me to attend classes.		2.88	0.66	Agreed
3.	I find it easier to continue my education despite being displaced due to access to technology.		3.00	0.78	Agreed
4.	Technology has facilitated my connection with teachers beyond the classroom, though access remains significantly limited		3.20	0.67	Agreed
5.	My access to educational resources has increased due to digital tools like computers or tablets.		2.93	0.90	Agreed
	Grand Mean		2.96	0.72	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 2 illustrates the role of technology in increasing access to education for IDP children in Benue State. All item statements have mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of

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2.96 and a standard deviation of 0.72, the findings suggest that technology has played a significant role in enhancing access to education for IDP children in Benue State.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools compared to traditional method on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Technology Impact on the Quality of Education Received by IDP Children in Benue State Compared to Traditional Methods

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	The use of technology has improved the quality of education I receive compared to traditional classroom methods.		2.98	0.89	Agreed
2.	Learning with digital tools (e.g., computers, tablets) provides a better understanding of the topics taught compared to traditional textbooks.		3.23	0.56	Agreed
3.	Technology has made learning more interactive and engaging compared to conventional classroom activities.		3.23	0.74	Agreed
4.	The quality of feedback I receive from teachers is better when using technology compared to traditional methods.		3.00	0.81	Agreed
5.	Online resources have provided me with access to more varied and up-to-date content compared to traditional methods.		2.72	0.87	Agreed
	Grand Mean		3.03	0.77	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 3 illustrates the extent to which technology has impacted the quality of education received by IDP children in Benue State compared to traditional methods. All item statements recorded mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of 3.03 and a standard deviation of 0.77, the findings suggest that technology has positively influenced the quality of education for IDP children.

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Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one revealed that technology has played a significant role in enhancing access to education for IDP children in Benue State. The rise in remote learning opportunities for IDP children in Benue State could be attributed to the growing availability of digital tools and online platforms. The outcome of the study was found to be similar with that of Oyelere, Suhonen, and Shonola (2016) which emphasized the role of technology in facilitating distance learning by providing students in remote areas with access to quality education through online courses and virtual classrooms. The result also concurred with that of Alimi, Babalola, Aladesusi, Issa, and Omolafe (2022), which opined that assistive technology is a vital tool in making learning accessible and meaningful for children with disabilities in Nigeria. The finding further agreed with that of Ripat and Woodgate (2017), which reported that assistive technology plays a significant role in overcoming academic challenges and enhancing the performance of children with disabilities. The implication of this finding is that the use of digital tools and assistive technologies can bridge educational gaps for IDP children in Benue State, providing them with better access to quality learning opportunities.

The finding of research question two showed that technology has positively influenced the quality of education for IDP children. The positive influence of technology on the quality of education for IDP children could be attributed to the increasing integration of digital resources in educational delivery. The findings of the study align with Baytak, Tarman, and Ayas (2011), who emphasized that the integration of technology into classrooms creates a more enjoyable, interactive, and meaningful learning environment for students. Similarly, the result resonates with Bulut and Delen (2011), who highlighted that information and communication technology positively impacts students' achievements in mathematics and science. Additionally, the finding corresponds with Herron (2010), who demonstrated that technology-based math lessons foster student engagement and retention through hands-on activities. Finally, it concurs with Courduff (2011), who reported that incorporating technology in special education supports students in achieving individual educational goals and enhances academic outcomes.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the significant role of technology in enhancing access to education for internally displaced persons (IDP) children in Benue State. The findings demonstrate that digital tools and platforms have expanded educational opportunities, making learning more accessible for displaced children. Additionally, technology has positively influenced the quality of education, offering improved instructional resources and fostering better learning outcomes. These results underscore the potential of technology to bridge educational gaps for IDP children, contributing to a more equitable and effective learning environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

1. Government and NGOs should prioritize initiatives that enhance access to education through mobile learning apps, offline educational content, and community-based technology hubs tailored to the needs of IDP children.
2. Educational policymakers should implement hybrid models that combine technology and traditional teaching, ensuring that technological tools complement rather than replace face-to-face interaction for enhanced learning outcomes.

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References

- Adewale, S., (2016). Internally displaced persons and the challenges of survival in Abuja. *African Security Review*, 25(2), pp. 176 – 192.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10246029.2016.1154475>

(*Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025*)

- Akume, A. T. (2015). The question of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Nigeria: A reflection on present realities. *Journal of Third World Studies*, 32(1), 221-244.
- Alimi, A. E., Babalola, E. O., Aladesusi, G. A., Issa, A. I., & Omolafe, E. V. (2022). Availability and Utilization of Assistive Technology for Learning among Students with Special Needs in Ilorin, Kwara State. *Indonesian Journal of Community and Special Needs Education*, 2(1), 17-28.
- Ambe-Uva, T.N. (2012). The right to education for internally displaced persons in Nigeria through open and distance learning. *Huria: Journal of the Open University of Tanzania / Vol. 13 No. 2 (2012) / Articles*
- Baytak, A., Tarman, B., & Ayas, C. (2011). Experiencing technology integration in education: children's perceptions. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 3(2), 139-151.
- Bekalo, S.A., Brophy, M. & Welford, A.G. (2003). The Development of Education in Post-Conflict 'Somaliland'. *International Journal on Educational Development*, (23), pp. 459-475.
- Bertoni, E., Maio, M. D., Molini, V. & Nistico, R. (2019). Education is forbidden: The effect of the Boko Haram conflict on education in North-East Nigeria. *Journal of Development Economics*, 141(102249).
- Bothe, D. A., Olness, K. N., & Reyes, C. (2018). Overview of Children and Disaster. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioural Pediatrics*, (39), pp. 653-662
- Bothe, D. A., Olness, K. N., & Reyes, C. (2018). Overview of children and disaster. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioural Pediatrics*, (39), pp. 653-662.
- Bulut, O., & Delen, E. (2011). The relationship between students' exposure to technology and their achievement in science and math. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 10(3).
- Courduff, J. (2011). One size never fits all: Tech integration for special needs. *Learning & Leading with Technology*, 38(8), 16-19.
- Dryden-Peterson, S., Dahya, N., & Adelman, E. (2017). Pathways to Educational Success Among Refugees: Connecting Locally and Globally Situated Resources. *American Educational Research Journal*, 54(6), pp. 1011-1047

(*Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025*)

Edmonds, R. R. (1979). Effective Schools for Urban Poor. *Educational Leadership*, 37, (1), pp. 15-27.

Ferris, E. & Winthrop, R. (2010). Education and displacement: assessing conditions for refugees and internally displaced persons affected by conflict. UNESCO. *Education for All Global Monitoring Report*.

Gibbs, G., Edited by, Flick, U. (2007). *Analysing Qualitative Data*. The SAGE Qualitative Research Kit. SAGE Publications Limited London.

Hansen, K., (2016). The Relationship between Teacher Perceptions of Pupils Attractiveness and Academic Ability. *British Educational Research Journal*, 42(3).

Herron, J. (2010). Implementation of technology in an elementary mathematics lesson: The experiences of pre-service teachers at one university. *SRATE Journal*, 19(1), International Society for Technology in Education. (2011). Top ten in '10: ISTE's education technology priorities for 2010. Retrieved from <http://www.iste.org/about-iste/advocacy/top-ten-in-10.aspx>.

Hogwood, B. W. & Gunn, L. A. (1984). *Policy analysis for the real world*. Oxford University Press, New York.

Howlett, M. & Ramesh, M. (2003). *Studying Public Policy: Policy Cycles and Policy Subsystems. Second Edition*. Oxford University Press Canada.

IDMC (2020). *Nigeria: Global report on internal displacement*. Norwegian Refugee Commission: Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre.

IDMC. (2017). Global report on internal displacement Norwegian Refugee Council. Retrieved from <http://www.internal-displacement.org/global-report/grid2017/>

Ingutia, R. (2020). Does marginalization in education stall the progress of the sustainable development goals? *International Journal of Primary, Elementary and Early Years Education*, 48(5), pp. 495-511

INSEC [Informal Sector Service Centre] (2007). *Human Rights Yearbook*. Kathmandu: INSEC

(*Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025*)

- Jones, N., Abebe, W., Emire, G., Gebeyehu, Y., Gezahegne, K., Tilahun, K., Workneh, F. & Vintges, J. (2022). Disrupted Educational Pathways: The effects of conflicts on adolescent educational access and learning in war-torn Ethiopia. *Frontiers in Education*. Available at: (DOI: 10.3389/feduc.2022.963415).
- Kelly, A. (2001). *Benchmarking for Improvement: A practical guide for comparing and improving effectiveness*. Routledge Falmer, New York.
- Kim, C., & Rouse, M. (2011). Reviewing the role of teachers in achieving Education for All in Cambodia. UNESCO IBE. Prospects, at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-011-9201-y> (41), pp. 415-428. Available.
- Kirk, J. & Winthrop R. (2007). Promoting Quality Education in Refugee Contexts: Supporting teacher development in Northern Ethiopia. *International Review of Education*, (53), pp. 715-723.
- Levine, D. U. & Lezotte, L. W. (1990). *Unusually Effective Schools: a Review and Analysis of Research and Practice*. Madison, WI: National Centre for Effective Schools Research and Development.
- Ling, M. (2017). Returning to No Home: Educational Remigration and Displacement in Rural China. George Washington University Institute for Ethnographic Research. *Anthropological Quarterly*, 90(3), pp. 715 – 742
- Macbeath, J. & Mortimore, P. (2001). *Improving school effectiveness*. St Edmundsbury Press Ltd.
- Mattina, G. L. (2018). How persistent is the effect of conflict on primary education? Long-run evidence from the Rwandan genocide. *Economics Letter*, (163), pp. 32 – 35.
- Messiou, K. (2012). *Confronting marginalisation in education: A Framework for promoting inclusion*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group London and New York.
- Mowat, J. G. (2015). Towards a new conceptualization of marginalization. *European Educational Research Journal*, 14(5), pp. 454 – 476.
- Murphy, J. (2011). Homeless children and youth at risk: the educational impact of displacement. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 16(1), pp. 38 – 55

(*Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025*)

National Emergency Management Agency (2015). Annual report. Abuja: Yaliman press Ltd

National Policy on Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria. Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2014). Available at: <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/5a7ae2324.pdf>.

Nigeria Displacement Tracking Matrix (2024). Round 25 November. Retrieved from <https://displacement.iom.int/Nigeria>.

Obashoro-John, O. A., & Oni, G. J., (2017). Refugee Education: The State of Nigeria's Preparedness. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5(6), pp. 989-994.

Olakulehin, F.K. (2007). Information and communication technologies in teacher training and professional development in Nigeria. Retrieved from http://gojde.anadolu.edu.tr/tojide25/pdf/article_11.pdf. *Turkish online Journal of Distance education*, 8(1), 133-142.

Olanrewaju, F. O., Olanrewaju, F. O., Alabi, J. O., Amoo, E., Loromeke, E. & Ajayi, L. A. (2019). Insurgency and the invisible displaced population in Nigeria: A Situational Analysis. *Original Research*, pp. 1-12. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2158244019846207>

Omale, A.A., & S, D. (2022). Education in emergencies and national development: bridging the gap in educating internally displaced children. *Zamfara Journal of Politics and Development*. Vol. 3 No. 3.

Onapajo, H. (2020). Children in Boko Haram Conflict: The Neglected Facet of a Decade of Terror in Nigeria. *African Security*, 13(2), pp. 195 – 211.

Oyelere, S.S., Suhonen, J., & Sutinen, E. (2016). "M-learning: a new paradigm of learning ICT in Nigeria", *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies (iJIM)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 35-44.

Ripat, J. D., & Woodgate, R. L. (2017). The importance of assistive technology in the productivity pursuits of young adults with disabilities. *Work*, 57(4), 455-468.

Stoll, L. & Fink, D. (1996). *Changing our schools*. Open University Press, Buckingham.

Tajudeen, O. A. & Fadeyi, A. O. (2013). Issues of refugees and displaced persons in Nigeria. *Journal of Sociological Research*, 4(1).

(*Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025*)

Thisday, (2023). *Experts seek increased access to education for disadvantaged children via technology*. Editorial. Thisday Newspaper. Monday, September 31.

Tinio, L.V. (2003). *ICT in education*. Retrieved on August 31st, 2011 from <http://www.en.wikibooks.org/wiki/ICT-in-Education>.

UNESCO (2007). *Manual for pilot testing the use of indicators to assess impact of ICT use in education*. Retrieved on October 1st, 2011 from <http://www.unescobkk.org/education/ICT/resources>.

UNESCO, (2019), Global education monitoring report, Summary, p.26. Retrieved 24th June 2021 from http://www.internaldisplacement.org/sites/default/files/publications/documents/Education%20for%20Internally%20Displaced%20Children_web.pdf.

UNESCO. (2023). *Out-of-school numbers are growing in sub-Saharan Africa | Global Education Monitoring Report*. <https://www.unesco.org/gem-report/en/2022-out-school>

UNHCR – United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2016) *Connecting refugees: how internet and mobile connectivity can improve refugee well-being and transform humanitarian action* (www.unhcr.org/media/connecting-refugees).

UNICEF (1997b). Population Estimates for Somaliland. UNICEF Zonal Office, Hargeisa.

Uzodinma, U.E., Njoku, O.C., & Ejiofor, J.N., (2024). Assessing the impact of technology integration in enhancing learning outcomes on childhood and primary education in Nigeria: a case study of hill crest preparatory and primary school, Nsukka. *International Journal of Studies in Education* – Vol. 20, Issue 2, 31-41.

Wilson, J.D. (1988). *Appraising teaching quality*. British Library Cataloguing Publication Data

World Bank (2002). *Information and communication technologies: a World Bank group strategy*. Washington, D.C: The World Bank Group.